

The Origin of Spurious Solutions in Periodic Bloch-Floquet FEM Eigenmode Formulations

Vasileios Salonikios and Michalis Nitas

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Thessaloniki, Greece

Abstract—We reveal the reason behind the appearance of spurious modes in periodic eigenmode FEM formulations. After the derivation of the eigenproblem of a Bloch-Floquet formulation, we solve for the dispersion diagram of a stratified medium and compare it with the one derived through the classical eigenvalue treatment in FEM. We illustrate the existence of periodic spurious modes and note their differences with respect to the well-documented dc modes in the literature. Finally, we present the explanation for their generative cause.

Index Terms—Bloch-Floquet wave propagation, Finite Element Method, nonphysical solutions, periodic media, spurious modes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Utilization of edge-based expansion functions for the correct approximation of tangentially-continuous fields in the Finite Element Method in electromagnetics is well-established [1], [2]. Based on the pioneer work of Bossavit and Nédélec [3]–[5], the curl operator in Maxwell’s equations was efficiently modeled, capable of properly integrating the properties of its range space for time-varying electromagnetic fields and its nullspace for static fields of zero frequency. Additionally, there has been an extensive research in the literature on the origin of spurious (dc) modes – i.e., the nonphysical solutions of a physical problem – and their elimination, due to the unavoidable inclusion of the gradient subspace in the expansion and test functions of the hierarchical basis functions: Imposition of the divergence condition by the development of constrained Lanczos algorithms for spurious DC modes suppression in single-field variable or field-flux FEM formulations, DC and imaginary mode suppression in lossy and unbounded structures, spurious mode elimination in reduced order models or the utilization of mixed spectral element methods [6]–[9].

A much less popular finite element approximation consists of the formulation which is based on the modified Bloch-periodic Helmholtz equation [10]. Initially, this FEM formulation was derived so as to fulfill the following purpose: In order to form the dispersion diagram for a periodic structure, the classical treatment followed in the literature of photonic crystals, is the span of the irreducible Brillouin zone and the search of the (eigen)frequency as an eigenvalue. The disadvantage of this approximation is the limitation of this process to return information inside bandgap frequency regions, where the propagation constant is imaginary. It is exactly this drawback that the Bloch-Floquet periodic finite element formulation comes to cover, i.e., the formation of the

dispersion diagram both for passband and for bandgap zones, where the frequency is the given parameter of the problem and the (complex) propagation constant is the eigenvalue.

In this work, for the first time in the literature, we reveal the reason behind the appearance of spurious modes in periodic Bloch-Floquet eigenvalue FEM formulations. We initially derive the finite element formulation for the electric field periodic envelope, based on the modified Bloch-Floquet Helmholtz equation. Subsequently, we solve an eigenmode problem of a typical periodic computational domain consisting of a stratified medium, with an existing analytical solution. Then we provide an explanation of the solutions returned by the numerical approximation, compared with the solution provided by the classical treatment of the problem in the FEM. Finally, we propose the required modification of the basis functions towards the purpose of elimination of these spurious numerical solutions.

II. FEM FORMULATION FOR THE BLOCH-FLOQUET ENVELOPE OF THE ELECTRIC FIELD

A. Governing Equations and Variational Formulations

We consider an electromagnetic structure consisting of potentially electrically and/ or magnetically lossy anisotropic media of relative electric permittivity $\bar{\epsilon}_r$ and relative magnetic permeability $\bar{\mu}_r$, which is periodic in one, two or three dimensions. Assuming that \mathbf{e} , \mathbf{h} , \mathbf{d} and \mathbf{b} are the periodic envelopes of the electric field, magnetic field, dielectric displacement and magnetic induction, respectively, $\mathbf{k} = k \hat{\mathbf{k}}$ is the Bloch-Floquet wavevector of prescribed propagation direction $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ (e.g. $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$) and $k = \beta - j\alpha$ is the complex propagation constant, the electromagnetic quantities of the modes supported by a periodic medium may be expressed according to the Bloch-Floquet theorem as

$$\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{e} e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} \quad (1a)$$

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{h} e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} \quad (1b)$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{d} e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}} \quad (1c)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{b} e^{-j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{r}}, \quad (1d)$$

whereas the constitutive relations between the Bloch-Floquet wave components are

$$\mathbf{d} = \epsilon_0 \bar{\epsilon}_r \mathbf{e} \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathbf{b} = \mu_0 \bar{\mu}_r \mathbf{h}. \quad (2b)$$

We obtain the modified Maxwell's curl equations in frequency domain in terms of the periodic envelope of the fields by substituting the transformed fields in the original Maxwell's equations and eliminating the exponential factors

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{e} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} = -j\omega\mathbf{b} = -j\omega\mu_0\bar{\bar{\mu}}_r\mathbf{h} \quad (3a)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{h} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{h} = j\omega\mathbf{d} = j\omega\epsilon_0\bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r\mathbf{e}. \quad (3b)$$

Taking the curl of Eq. (3a) and substituting Eq. (3b) in the resulting equation, we arrive at the modified Helmholtz equation for Bloch-Floquet wave propagation

$$\begin{aligned} & \nabla \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{e} - jk\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{e} - jk\nabla \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} \\ & - k^2 \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} - \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} \bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r \mathbf{e} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

We move on to the next step and derive the Galerkin formulation for Eq. (4). By using test function \mathbf{e}' , integrating over the volume V of the computational domain and applying Gauss' theorem, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & k^2 \iiint_V \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} dV \\ & + jk \iiint_V \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{e} dV \\ & - jk \iiint_V \nabla \times \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} dV \\ & + \iiint_V \nabla \times \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{e} dV - \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} \iiint_V \mathbf{e}' \cdot \bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r \mathbf{e} dV \\ & = \oint_S (\mathbf{e}' \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{e}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} dS - jk \oint_S (\mathbf{e}' \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} dS. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Boundary conditions of several types may be easily imposed (e.g., Impedance Boundary Condition - IBC, Absorbing Boundary Condition of 1st Type - ABC) via the surface terms, whereas it is also noted that imposition of Periodic Boundary Conditions (PBC) eliminates the surface terms due to the equality of the field quantities at master and slave periodic boundaries [6], [11]–[14].

B. Basis Functions and Discretization

The weak formulation of Eq. (5) is approximated with a finite dimensional problem, by the discretization of the electric field periodic envelope \mathbf{e} using finite element spaces: Expanding \mathbf{e} in the finite dimensional subset of $H(\text{curl}, \Omega)$, consisting of tangentially continuous edge-type basis functions of first order as $\mathbf{e} = \sum_{j=1}^6 e_j \mathbf{w}_j$ (where $\mathbf{w}_j = \zeta_{j,1} \nabla \zeta_{j,2} - \zeta_{j,2} \nabla \zeta_{j,1}$ are the basis functions corresponding to each one of the six tetrahedral edges connecting nodes $(j, 1)$ and $(j, 2)$ and e_j are the degrees of freedom corresponding to each edge) and using the same basis functions for the test fields $\mathbf{e}' = \sum_{i=1}^6 e'_i \mathbf{w}_i$, we derive the matrix form of the eigenvalue problem

$$\left\{ k^2 [\mathbf{M}] + k \left([\mathbf{Q}] - [\mathbf{P}] \right) + [\mathbf{S}] + [\mathbf{T}_s] \right\} \mathbf{e} = \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} [\mathbf{T}] \mathbf{e} \quad (6)$$

where the corresponding submatrices are calculated as follows:

$$[\mathbf{M}] = \iiint_V \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{w}_i \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{w}_j dV \quad (7a)$$

$$[\mathbf{Q}] = j \iiint_V \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{w}_i \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_j dV \quad (7b)$$

$$[\mathbf{P}] = -j \iiint_V \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_i \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{w}_j dV \quad (7c)$$

$$[\mathbf{S}] = \iiint_V \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_i \cdot \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{w}_j dV \quad (7d)$$

$$[\mathbf{T}] = \iiint_V \mathbf{w}_i \cdot \bar{\bar{\epsilon}}_r \mathbf{w}_j dV. \quad (7e)$$

$$\begin{aligned} [\mathbf{T}_s] &= \oint_S (\mathbf{w}' \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \nabla \times \mathbf{w}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} dS \\ &- jk \oint_S (\mathbf{w}' \times \bar{\bar{\mu}}_r^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{w}) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}} dS. \end{aligned} \quad (7f)$$

The sparse system of linear equations in Eq. (6) may be treated as a linear eigenvalue problem with the angular frequency ω as the eigenvalue of the problem and the degrees of freedom of the electric field periodic envelope \mathbf{e} as the eigenvector. In this case, the propagation constant $k = \beta$ is the known parameter of the problem, which may obtain values which span the Irreducible Brillouin Zone limits of the considered computational domain, i.e., $0 \leq \beta \leq \pi/d$, where d is the periodicity of the structure. (Of course, this treatment is in contrast to the original reason for deriving a Bloch-Floquet formulation, which is to solve the eigenvalue problem the other way round, i.e., with ω as a known parameter and the complex propagation constant γ as the eigenvalue). We cast the eigenproblem in the described form, so as it can be compared to the classical treatment of a periodic eigenvalue problem, where the derived Galerkin formulation of the standard Helmholtz equation yields an eigenvalue problem of the form

$$([\mathbf{S}] + [\mathbf{T}_s]) \mathbf{E} = \frac{\omega^2}{c_0^2} [\mathbf{T}] \mathbf{E}, \quad (8)$$

where the phase difference $e^{-j\beta d}$ between master and slave periodic boundaries is, at this case, embedded inside the $[\mathbf{S}]$ and $[\mathbf{T}]$ matrices, as is well-documented in the literature [15].

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Periodic Stratified Medium

We now turn our attention to the numerical evaluation of the derived formulations in Section II. To this end, we consider the periodic structure depicted in Fig. 1, the unit cell of which consists of a stratified dielectric medium of two dielectric slabs with dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_{r,1} = 1$ and $\epsilon_{r,2} = 9$. The structure is periodic in all three dimensions and its analytical solution is extracted in [16]. Propagation in x -axis is assumed, i.e. $k = \beta_x \hat{\mathbf{x}}$. It is noted that all simulations were carried out both in Comsol MultiphysicsTM and in in-house MatlabTM codes, exhibiting identical results for identical FEM meshes and eigenvalue solver tolerances (set to 10^{-9}).

Fig. 1. Unit cell of a dielectric stratified medium. It consists of two layers of air ($\epsilon_{r,1} = 1$) and width of $d_{x,1} = 0.2$ m and a layer dielectric permittivity of $\epsilon_{r,2} = 9$ and $d_{x,2} = 0.1$ m.

Fig. 2. Dispersion diagram of the structure in Fig. 1 corresponding to the solution of Eq. (8). Numerical values coincide with the theoretical ones, while non-physical dc modes appear at every simulated value of β_x .

In order to solve for all the eigenvalues of the problem, the computational domain is discretized by a coarse mesh of 770 tetrahedral elements resulting to 910 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the linear systems (6) and (8) are treated as dense matrix problems and solved by dense matrix solvers (Matlab's eig() function is utilized to return all the eigenpairs in the in-house code implementation). Figs. 2 and 3 illustrate the dispersion diagrams $\omega(\beta)$ for the cases of the classical treatment [Eq. (8)] and the Bloch-Floquet wave formulations [Eq. (6)], along with the analytical solution. Clearly, both numerical approximations converge to the theoretically expected values for all β values. These are the modes referred to as Type-B eigenmodes in the literature. Additionally high-frequency modes are also returned (type-C eigenmodes) which are modes that are insufficiently approximated by the finite element mesh, due to their much smaller propagating wavelength with respect to the mesh dimensions. Of course, a more dense mesh is capable of approximating more (physical) higher order modes of a structure, and type-C modes are predicted to appear in higher frequencies [17].

For the case of the classical formulation, it is observed that the eigenvalue solver converges to eigenmodes with

Fig. 3. Dispersion diagram of the structure in Fig. 1 corresponding to the solution of Eq. (6). Numerical values coincide with the theoretical ones, while the “periodic spurious” modes now appear at every simulated value of β_x .

Fig. 4. A detailed (zoomed) plot of the “periodic spurious” modes appearing in the dispersion diagram of Fig. 3. The returned modes follow the depicted distribution, with an ascending eigenfrequency as β_x increases. The number of returned eigenmodes is equal to the number of the mesh nodes (which is equal to 130 for the simulated computational domain)

eigenfrequencies very close to zero. These are the so-called non physical (spurious) dc-modes, which are depicted in Fig. 2 in red color. Their existence is well-documented in the literature, where it is reported that they consist of nonphysical dc spurious modes and their number is equal to the number of nodes in the finite element mesh [17]. Algebraically they are returned due to the nullity of the $[\mathbf{S}]$ matrix, i.e., they are related to the $[\mathbf{S}]\mathbf{E} = \lambda\mathbf{E}$ problem. Indeed, in our case, the solver returns 130 modes with eigenvalues close to zero

Fig. 5. Electric field distribution (E_z component) of a returned “periodic spurious” mode corresponding to a given $\beta_x = 3$ rad/m and a returned eigenfrequency of 0.1×10^7 Hz. Its spurious nature is easily observed as it contains random non-zero field areas, not corresponding to an expected harmonically time-varying electromagnetic field distribution.

Fig. 6. Returned eigenvalues of the periodic formulation (Eq. 6) with ω set to zero. Their distribution is the same as the one returned from the original problem's solution (Eq. 8) with an ascending eigenfrequency as β_x increases.

(< 200 Hz) whereas the solution of the $[\mathbf{S}]\mathbf{E} = \lambda\mathbf{E}$ equation leads to $N=130$ modes with dc eigenvalues, as well, with this solution's corresponding eigenvalues being, also, close to zero.

B. Existence and Origin of the "Periodic Spurious" Modes

We now focus on the solution of Eq.(6), where the zoomed version of its dispersion diagram is presented in Fig. 4. It is easily observed that there is a distribution of returned modes, with eigenfrequencies which are obviously not numerically close to zero – as in the case of the solution of Eq. (8) – but with an increasing eigenfrequency as β increases, following the specific illustrated pattern. The number of these *periodic spurious* eigenvalues is equal to the number of nodes of the finite element mesh, in this case, too (130). In Fig. 5, a typical field distribution (xy -slice) of such a mode is illustrated, where its spurious nature is obvious, as it constitutes of an almost zero field distribution all over the computational domain, with a non-propagating (time-varying) nature.

Paralleling the two presented eigenproblems, we correlate the eigensolution of the periodic formulation [(Eq. (6))] with the eigensolution of the same problem in which we set $\omega = 0$. The returned eigenvalues of the latter problem are depicted in Fig. 6. It is clearly concluded that their distribution is the same as the one from the original eigenvalue problem. Furthermore, the returned eigenvectors' field representation are similar with the ones depicted in Fig. 5, both illustrating a spurious field distribution with numerically zero field components all over the computational domain. It is, therefore, clearly observed that in the case of the periodic formulation the return of the spurious solutions differentiates from the classical problem, as the spurious (with the meaning of nonphysical, not expected from the analytical electromagnetic solutions) modes appear to be converging to non-dc eigenfrequencies (ω values are not close to zero – at the level of some Hz – anymore).

In order to explain the nature of the described periodic spurious modes, we take a closer look at the modified Faraday's equation (3a). it is observed that when ω is set to zero then the equation $\nabla \times \mathbf{e} - j\kappa\hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{e} = 0$ is satisfied by a field of the form

$$\mathbf{e} = -\nabla\phi + j\kappa\phi\hat{\mathbf{k}}. \quad (9)$$

In other words, the modified curl operator in Eq. (3a) produces a new nullspace, in which the vectorial field quantity $j\kappa\phi\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ has to be added to $-\nabla\phi$, which is the nullspace of the initial (unmodified) operator. Furthermore, Eq. (9) also satisfies the governing equation (4) at dc ($\omega = 0$), therefore this field quantity constitutes the nullspace of the modified Helmholtz operator, as well.

The returned eigenvalues are not (numerically) zero, because the utilized basis functions of 1st order fail to approximate correctly the new nullspace $\mathbf{e} = -\nabla\phi + j\kappa\phi\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ and falsely force the solver to converge to solutions identical to the solutions of the modified Helmholtz formulation with $\omega = 0$. Indeed, the eigensolution of the periodic formulation is "contaminated" by this false approximation and returns (130 in our case) non-zero eigenvalues, in the place of the expected dc-modes (as ω is set to zero). This incomplete representation of the modified nullspace appears to be the main reason for the convergence of the formulation of the governing equation to the described periodic spurious eigenpairs.

IV. CONCLUSION

The original basis functions, constructed in the pioneer works of Bossavit, were specifically designed to conform with the original curl operator, and, thus, they are capable of correctly approximating a static field. Through our analysis, it is clear that utilization of the same functions to approximate the modified nullspace is problematic, as it fails to approximate the new, modified curl operator. Unless the basis functions are properly modified, so as to include the additional potential term in their subspace, the incomplete nullspace representation will cause the solvers' convergence to the periodic spurious modes. It is finally noted that the appearing spurious modes in an $\omega - \gamma$ process are exactly the same with the described ones in a $\beta - \omega$ process of a Bloch-Floquet FEM formulation.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. P Webb, "Edge elements and what they can do for you." *IEEE Transactions on magnetics* vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 1460-1465, 1993.
- [2] J. P Webb, "Hierarchical vector basis functions of arbitrary order for triangular and tetrahedral finite elements." *IEEE Transactions on antennas and propagation* vol. 47, no. 8, pp. 1244-1253, 1999.
- [3] A. Bossavit, "Computational Electromagnetism: Variational Formulations, Complementarity, Edge Elements." *New York, NY, USA: Academic* 1998.
- [4] J. C. Nédélec, "Mixed finite elements in R^3 ." *Numer. Math.* vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 315-341, 1980.
- [5] J. C. Nédélec, "A new family of mixed finite elements in R^3 ." *Numer. Math.* vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 57-81, 1986.
- [6] S. G. Perepelitsa, R. Dyczij-Edlinger and Jin-Fa Lee "Finite-element analysis of arbitrarily shaped cavity resonators using H/sup 1/(curl) elements" *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics* vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 1776-1779, 1997.
- [7] Y. Zhu and A. C. Cangellaris "Robust finite-element solution of lossy and unbounded electromagnetic eigenvalue problems." *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* vol. 50, no. 10, pp. 2331-2338, 2002.
- [8] C. L. Zekios, P. C. Allilomes and G. A. Kyriacou "DC and imaginary spurious modes suppression for both unbounded and lossy structures." *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* vol. 63, no. 7, pp. 2082-2093, 2015.
- [9] V. De La Rubia, D. Young, G. Fotyga, and M. Mrozowski, "Spurious modes in model order reduction in variational problems in electromagnetics." *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques* vol. 70, no. 11, pp. 5159-5171, 2022.

- [10] C. Fietz, Y. Urzhumov, and G. Shvets, "Complex k band diagrams of 3D metamaterial/photonic crystals," *Optics Express*, vol. 19, no. 20, pp. 19027-19041, 2011.
- [11] M. Nitas, V. Salonikios, and T. V. Yioultsis, "Alternative finite element eigenvalue formulations for the simulation of arbitrarily bianisotropic media," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, **71**, 570-578, 2023.
- [12] M. Nitas, *et al.*, "Numerical calculation of dispersion diagrams and field distributions of waves in 3-D periodic split-ring resonator media," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 55, no. 12, pp. 1-4, 2019.
- [13] M. Nitas and T. V. Yioultsis, "Comparison of split-ring resonator composite periodic media based on numerical eigensolutions," *2021 15th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, pp.1-4, IEEE, 2021.
- [14] V. Salonikios, M. Nitas, S. Raptis, and T. V. Yioultsis, "Computational analysis of graphene-based periodic structures via a three-dimensional field-flux eigenmode Finite Element formulation," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research*, vol. 92, pp. 157-167, 2020.
- [15] C. Mias, J. P. Webb, and R. L. Ferrari, "Finite element modeling of electromagnetic waves in doubly and triply periodic structures," *Proc. Inst. Elect. Eng. Optoelectron.*, vol. 145, pp. 111-118, 1999.
- [16] A. Tavallaei and J. Webb, "Finite-element modeling of evanescent modes in the stopband of periodic structures," *IEEE Trans. Mag.*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 1358-1361, 2008.
- [17] J. Jin, "The finite element method in electromagnetics," *John Wiley & Sons*, 2015.